

SeGuL Supplementary Material

Daniel D. Reidpath and Mark R. Diamond

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Background

In the tradition of literary programming, this R Markdown document is both an explanation of the SeGuL simulation and the simulation itself.¹ The document is broken up into four distinct sections:

1. Functions (called during the execution of the simulation);
2. Initialisation (of key variables);
3. Main (loop, for running the simulation); and
4. Results (for displaying Figures and Tables described in Diamond & Reidpath (1993/2024)).

Functions

There are three core functions to the self guided, inductive learning simulation:

- A case generation function that will be used to generate sets of n cases at a time: `generate_case()`;
- A case selection function which will select the “best” positive case from a set of n cases: `select_case()`; and
- A function to update rule for case selection based on the addition of the newly selected case: `update_rule()`.

Diamond and Reidpath (1993) described the “rule” for selecting cases according to the following procedure:

1. For each of the five current cases (in round $i + 1$) calculate: $value = a_{i1}x_1 + a_{i2}x_2 + \dots + a_{i6}x_6$, where “ $a_{i1}, a_{i2}, \dots, a_{i6}$ ” represented the rule R_i .
2. Select the case for which value was greatest, and add the case to the list L.

In other words, for each block of five cases, select $max(value)$ and add that case to the database of predicted positive cases (which is used as the learning database to update the selection rule).

```
# Function to generate a case(s)
generate_case <- function(cutoff = "random", n = 1) {
  # Generate 'n' sets of 6 random normal deviates for attributes (x1 to x6)
  x_values <- matrix(rnorm(6 * n), ncol = 6)

  # Calculate the sum of x_values for each set
  sums <- rowSums(x_values)

  # Determine 'y_values' based on 'cutoff'
  y_values <- switch(
    cutoff,
    "EW50" = as.integer(sums > 0),           # Criterion EW50
    "EW27" = as.integer(sums > 1.5),        # Criterion EW27
    "EW5"  = as.integer(sums > 4),          # Criterion EW5
  )
}
```

¹doi:10.5281/zenodo.10931640

```

"XOR" = {
  result <- numeric(n)
  for (i in 1:n) {
    result[i] <- ifelse(xor(sum(x_values[i, 1:3]) > 1.5, sum(x_values[i, 4:6]) > 1.5), 1, 0)
  }
  result
},
"random" = sample(0:1, n, replace = TRUE), # Random data for seeding
stop("Invalid cutoff specified.")
)

# Create the resulting data frame
data <- data.frame(x1 = x_values[, 1],
                  x2 = x_values[, 2],
                  x3 = x_values[, 3],
                  x4 = x_values[, 4],
                  x5 = x_values[, 5],
                  x6 = x_values[, 6],
                  y = y_values)

return(data)
}

# Function to select a case based on the rule
select_case <- function(cases, rule) {
  # Calculate the weighted sum for each row using matrix multiplication
  weighted_sum <- as.matrix(cases[, 1:6]) %*% rule

  # Find the row index with the maximum weighted sum
  max_row_index <- which.max(weighted_sum)

  # Return the row with the maximum weighted sum
  selected_case <- cases[max_row_index, ]

  return(selected_case)
}

# Function to update the rule using linear regression
update_rule <- function(L) {
  # Fit a linear regression model and extract the Rule
  lm(y ~ x1 + x2 + x3 + x4 + x5 + x6, data = L)$coef[2:7] # Exclude the intercept (b0)
}

```

Initialisation

Four objects need to be initialised at the beginning of the simulation:

- A database (dataframe) of 8 uninformative cases from which to seed SeGuL: L ;
- The initial rule on which to select cases: R ;
- An integer for the number of cases to be simultaneously evaluated by `case_select()`: n . In Diamond & Reidpath(1993) we evaluated blocks of 5 cases at a time, and we stick to that here; and

- The number of times SeGuL selects 1 case from n cases: *number_of_iterations*.

The main difference between the approach we take here and the approach we took in 1993 is that, in 1993 we generated a database of 3,000 cases ahead of time. Here, we do it on-the-fly. The SeGuLer looped through the database evaluating blocks of 5 cases at a time. That means there were 600 total iterations. We preserve that in the code below. However, in generating the random data ahead of time (in 1993), we could guarantee that the intercorrelation matrix between the predictors (x_1, \dots, x_n) contained only low values ($r < .05$). Here we can only be certain that the data intercorrelation matrix will tend to low values but, by chance alone, some r may be $> .05$.

```
# Initialise
iL <- generate_case("random", 8) # Seed the database with 8 uninformative cases
iR <- update_rule(iL) # Generate an initial (uninformed) rule
n <- 5 # Evaluate 5 cases at a time
number_of_iterations <- 600

# For generating the results, rather than a core part of SeGuL
# Keep a copy of the data generated on the fly
db <- iL[, 1:6] # Start with the 8 uninformative seed cases
# Keep a copy of the Rules
ia_weights <- as.data.frame(matrix(iR, ncol = 6))
colnames(ia_weights) <- paste0("a", 1:6)
# create an empty list to store outputs
outputs <- list()
```

Main

This is the main learning loop for SeGuL.

```
# Main loop for SeGuL algorithm
for(i in c("EW50", "EW27", "EW5", "XOR")){
  set.seed(9361) # This ensures that the "database" of cases will be the same for each i
  L <- iL # set the initial condition for the seed prior to each model EW50, EW27, EW5
  R <- iR # set the initial rule
  a_weights <- ia_weights # Create the a_weights record

  for (j in 1:number_of_iterations) {
    # "Read" next n cases from the database
    cases <- generate_case(i, n)

    # Select case
    selected_case <- select_case(cases, R)
    L <- rbind(L, selected_case)

    # Update rule
    R <- update_rule(L)
    a_weights <- rbind(a_weights, R) # Record changing rules

    # Save new cases into the "database"
    if(i == "EW50"){
      db <- rbind(db, cases[, 1:6])
    }
  }
}
# Add outputs to a list
```

```

outputs[[i]] <- list(L = L, a_weights = a_weights)
}

```

Results

We start by looking at the correlation matrix of the 3000 cases generated during the simulation. The random number generator we used in 1993 was not great and it took some work to ensure that none of the possible pairs drawn from x_1, \dots, x_6 had an $r > .05$. In this data set, the maximum off-diagonal correlation was 0.026.

Table 2

Optimal positive case selection (OSR), the actual positive case selection rate (ASR), and the base rate of positive cases for each of the four learners: the three equal weights models (EW_{50} , EW_{27} , and EW_5), and the logical exclusive or (XOR) model.

Mode	OSR	ASR	Base rate
EW_{50}	97	95	50
EW_{27}	79	75	27
EW_5	23	21	5
XOR	85	56	31

Table 3

The distribution of cases selected during the XOR simulation.

	$w_1 < 1.5$	$w_1 > 1.5$
$w_2 < 1.5$	210	306
$w_2 > 1.5$	30	62

Figures 4a..4d

```

aweight_plot <- function(aw_frame, p_title = "Learning over time"){
  p <- aw_frame %>%
    mutate(row_number = row_number()) %>%
    pivot_longer(
      cols = a1:a6,
      names_to = "variable",
      values_to = "value"
    ) %>%
    ggplot(aes(x = row_number, y = value, color = variable, group = variable)) +
    geom_line() +
    theme_minimal() +
    theme(legend.position = "none") +
    labs(x = "Selected cases", y = "Weight", title = p_title)

  return(p)
}

p50 <- aweight_plot(outputs$EW50$a_weights[9:608,], p_title = "EW50")

```

```

p27 <- aweight_plot(outputs$EW27$a_weights[9:608,], p_title = "EW27")
p5 <- aweight_plot(outputs$EW5$a_weights[9:608,], p_title = "EW5")
pxor <- aweight_plot(outputs$XOR$a_weights[9:608,], p_title = "XOR")

```

```
(p50 + p27)/(p5 + pxor)
```


Figure 1: Learning over time